

**THE THREAT OF VIOLENCE IN PART 3 OF ARTICLE 342 OF THE
CRIMINAL CODE OF UKRAINE: CURRENT ISSUES
OF LAW ENFORCEMENT**

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Annotation. The part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine establishes the grounds for criminal liability for qualified resistance. Resistance combined with coercion of a representative of the authorities, a state executive, a member of a public formation for the protection of public order and the state border or a military officer, an authorized person of the Individual Deposit Guarantee Fund through violence or the threat of using such violence to perform clearly illegal actions.

The combination of such terms as “coercion,” “violence,” “threat of using violence,” “obviously illegal actions” in one part of the prohibitive criminal law significantly complicates its application in practice.

Key words: coercion, violence, threat of using violence, obviously illegal actions.

Let’s pay attention to the interpretation of the content of the threat of violence, which is carried out with the aim of forcing the victims to perform clearly illegal actions.

The threat of using violence in the theory of criminal law is interpreted in different ways: as a promise to use it immediately [1, p. 798]; as statements or actions that indicate the intention of the guilty person to use violence against the victim [2, p. 1106; 3, p. 769]; as actions or statements expressing the perpetrator's intention to use physical violence against the victim [4, p. 718]; as intimidating the victim with any physical violence [5, p. 1052].

Coercion through the threat of violence includes statements (verbal threats) or actions (gestures, facial expressions, display of weapons, etc.) that indicate the real intentions of the guilty person to use physical violence against the victim [6, p. 322].

The threat of using violence may consist of a promise to affect not only the victim's health, bodily integrity, and personal will, but also other goods belonging to him, such as property [1, p. 798]. Therefore, the victim may be threatened with murder, bodily harm, deprivation of liberty, destruction or damage to property, etc.

The threat to a representative of the authorities, a state executive, a member of a public formation for the protection of public order and the state border, or a military serviceman, an authorized person of the Individual Deposit Guarantee Fund must be real. That is, the victim must be aware that violence will be immediately applied to him/her, although the subject may not have the intention to do so [1, p. 798-799].

Regarding the qualification of the threat, the views of scientists are ambiguous. V. A. Klymenko notes that the threat of murder, bodily harm, or deprivation of liberty to a law enforcement officer does not require additional qualifications under Art. 345 of the Criminal Code [3, p. 769]. Instead, H. Ye. Boldar emphasizes that modern judicial practice proceeds from the fact that the threat of murder, violence, or destruction or damage to property during resistance to a representative of a law enforcement agency is qualified under Part 2 or 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code and Part 1 of Art. 345 of the Criminal Code [6, p. 323]. Some scientists do not indicate at all how to correctly qualify the corresponding criminally illegal acts in such situations.

This position of scientists is probably caused by different interpretations of the term “threat of violence” used in Part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code. In practice, a valid question arises as to whether appropriate threats of violence to a representative of the government, an employee of a law enforcement agency, a state enforcer, a private enforcer, a member of a public organization for the protection of public order and the state border, or a military officer, an authorized person of the Individual Deposit Guarantee Fund with the aim of forcing them to fulfill clearly illegal actions, part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code do they require qualification in combination with other articles of this code?

In fact, this provision constitutes a compound crime. Part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code consists of resistance and other crimes consisting of violence (beatings, light, moderate, serious bodily injuries) or threats of such violence. The structure of the compound crime provided for in Part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code, gives rise to a number of problems regarding the qualification of relevant criminal acts. It is about non-compliance with the general rule of qualifying compound crimes under one article as a single crime, and not as a set of crimes [7, p. 41]. In addition, the creation of compound crimes by adding a qualifying feature, which is an independent component of the crime, is a violation of the principle of “non bis in idem” even at the stage of law-making, the consequences of which are manifested during the entire period of validity and application of the Criminal Code [8, p. 103-104].

According to the mentioned threats of violence to coerce the victims, provided for in part 1, 2 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code, the performance of clearly illegal actions should be qualified only under Part 3 of Art. 342 of the Criminal Code. In the opposite case, there will be a violation of the principle of “non bis in idem,” as well as the rules of qualification of compound crimes under one article as a single crime.

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